

Malya Indonesia's Digital Transformation Design in Business Development

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Fashion industry is one of the sub-sectors of the creative economy in Indonesia. Currently, the fashion industry ranks second in the number of creative economy businesses or companies with a contribution of 18.01% or around Rp. 116 trillion annually for the creative economy in Indonesia. Besides being one of the worships in fulfilling Islamic sharia in covering *aurat* for Muslim women, hijab is one of the fashion trends that interest modern society. The market and Muslim population in Indonesia have the potential to encourage entrepreneurs to take a significant part in the hijab fashion business. The digital transformation will include strategy context, strategy content, and strategy process. Malya Indonesia is one of the creative economy sub-sectors in the fashion sector that focuses on the hijab commodity. There are a few aspects that drive Malya Indonesia to transform digitally. Therefore, the company needs to change several components and its business model. This research is qualitative descriptive-analytical. Data collection techniques were done using interviews, observation, and documents study. By identifying the components of digital transformation, namely strategy context, content, and process the researcher will be able to create a new digital-based business model.

Keywords: DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, STRATEGY, BUSINESS MODEL

Introduction

The fashion industry is one of the sub-sectors of the creative economy in Indonesia. Currently, the fashion industry ranks second in the number of creative economy businesses or companies with a contribution of 18.01% or around Rp.116 trillion annually in the creative economy in Indonesia (Mia, 2019). One of the current fashion trends is fashion hijab, according to a report by Reuters in collaboration with the DinarStandard "State of the Global Islamic Economy Report", Muslim consumers spent approximately \$243 billion on clothing in 2015. Especially for Muslim fashion, the figure in that year reached 44 billion or 18% of the overall market (Republica.co.id, 2021). Based on the research of Fitrika (2016) which states that in addition to being one of

the worship in fulfilling Islamic sharia in covering *aurat* for Muslim women, hijab is one of the fashion trends that are quite in demand in modern society today. With various models and their easy-to-use concept, the hijab trend makes veiled Muslim women feel confident that they can also look beautiful and fashionable. Hijab is considered a modern fashion trend where women flock to use it for the sake of trends. Time after time, the hijab trend quickly spread and became one of the primary needs among the community.

The existence of a Muslim market and population in Indonesia has the potential to encourage entrepreneurs in Indonesia to take a significant part in the hijab fashion business. This industry is also inseparable from the role of technology and cyber traffic. An analysis done by Arianti Dwijayanti revealed that 48% of internet users search about hijab fashion on Google. Meanwhile, 32% are looking for hijab wear tutorials, 13% are looking for current hijab trends and 7% are looking for hijab styles. It concludes that hijab fashion business entrepreneurs need to include digitalization in the development of their business which increases the awareness among businesspeople about the power of the internet and digital devices in sales. According to (Delloite, 2015) 38% of business owners state that digital website devices are important for them to interact with consumers, while 32% and 23% choose social media and mobile messaging applications in interacting with consumers, and businesses are proven to experience an increase in revenue up to 80%.

Digital transformation can be interpreted as a deep and accelerating transformation of business activities, processes, competencies, and business models that fully take advantage of the changes and opportunities brought by digital technology and their impact across society in a strategic and prioritized manner (Sow, 2018). Performing digital transformation will include strategy context, strategy content, and strategy process (Mariam H. Ismail, 2017). The strategy context describes why the company needs to perform digital transformation by identifying the internal and external drivers of the company. Strategy content identifies the form of digital transformation that has been carried out by the company, and the strategy process identifies how the company performs the digital transformation.

Malya Indonesia is one of the subsectors of the creative economy in the field of fashion which focused on hijab commodities. The company, located in Bandung, started its business in 2014. The name Malya Indonesia itself is inspired by the daughter of the business owner's name. The owner of Malya Indonesia intends to change the mindset that women in hijab are not fashionable to be more fashionable with more innovative designs that suit the current trends. Starting from robes, pashmina, printed scarfs, tunics, blouse and pants. Malya Indonesia has a business model that focuses on selling products to end customers and resellers. Malya products, especially the scarfs have unique characteristics and designs that are difficult for competitors to imitate, this creates a product differentiation that can eventually bring Malya to survive to this day. In addition, the materials used are high quality with an economist selling price. Malya Indonesia expects a renewal of the business model over time. In addition, Malya Indonesia wants to include digitalization in its daily business processes. Digitalization is considered to be able to bring the company to be more capable in reading consumer interests and can reach a wider market reach. Malya feels the need to follow the digital transformation where it includes internet technology in its business processes. It is done to make the market interest in product

development easier to predict. In addition, the company can also see the level of customer satisfaction from the customer assessment feature and can build the company from criticism and advice columns.

With competition in the creative economy subsector of hijab fashion commodities, Malya Indonesia feels that its business needs to grow. Malya Indonesia wants to involve digital transformation with the intention of changing its business model to be more superior and have a wider market reach. Competition in similar business industries includes buttonscraft, yarashyma.id, myladyhijab, kinaya.id, Deenay, and Monel. This competition is dominating because of the Muslim hijab fashion community in Bandung. On the basis presented, the researcher is interested in knowing more about the business model that has been and t will be implemented in the future for the company and its industry. The title or topic taken of this research is "Digital Transformation Design in Business Development of Malya Indonesia".

Literature Review

Strategy

According to managers, strategy is a large-scale plan, with a future orientation to interact with competitive conditions to achieve company goals (J, 2011). Strategy is an archetype of current and planned goals for the deployment of resources and interactions between an organization and its market, competitors, and other environmental factors (Mullins, 2012). Strategy is a way to achieve long-term goals. Business strategies can include geography, diversification, acquisitions, product development, market penetration, savings, divestment, liquidation, and joint ventures (David, 2011).

Business Transformation

The fundamental change in organizational logic results in or is caused by a fundamental change in behavior. The four stages in the concept of transformation are (Mariam H. Ismail, 2017);

- Re-engineering; improve the efficiency of the organization as a whole while only partially addressing the better engagement of the workforce;
- Restructuring; increase efficiency without necessarily increasing the organization's ability to achieve long-term goals and seize opportunities;
- Renewing; obtain increased efficiency, effectivity, and innovation through employee empowerment without a clear focus on the desired results;
- Regeneration; improve existing processes and fundamentally review the direction and portfolio of available opportunities.

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is a deep and accelerating transformation with its business activities, processes, competencies, and business models so as to fully take advantage of the changes and opportunities brought by digital technology and its impact across society in a strategic and prioritized manner (Sow, 2018). Digital transformation includes the digitization of sales and communication channels, which provide new ways to interact and engage with customers, and the digitization of company offerings (products and services), which replaces or augments the physical form of offerings. Digital transformation also describes the trigger for a

business move or strategy with data-driven sources and digital business models that enable the creation of new ways of value creation (Haffke, 2016). Digital transformation is related to digital changes in technology that can lead companies to create new business models, by producing changed products or organizational structures, or process automation. With this change, it can be observed that there is an increase in demand based on data from the internet, which has led to changes in the entire business model (Hess, 2016). Digital transformation is defined as an organization's shift to big data, analytics cloud, mobile platforms, and social media. On the organization of change and development as a direct response to the changing business landscape, digital transformation is also defined as a change that is built on the foundation of digital technology that leads companies to unique changes in operations, processes, and value creation (Abdelaal, 2018). Digital transformation includes major changes that occur in society and the industrial environment through the use of digital technology. Digital transformation is also considered to have led companies to find ways to innovate using technology by designing new strategies and encouraging better operational performance (Vial, 2019). Digital transformation has a strategic approach, namely;

Strategy Context, ie internally the strategic context focuses on the business environment on cost savings, increasing emphasis on achieving operational efficiency improvements, effectiveness through appropriate information management. Externally, the company has reaped the benefits of improved cost and technological performance that has led to the emergence of information technology-based products and services.

Strategy Content (Decision Areas), from a business point of view, a case is made where long-term goals must be clear and go beyond the pursuit of quick profits. This relates to the need to assess the readiness to change, to understand the current state of the company's performance, to identify problems, vulnerabilities, opportunities, and risks. Digital transformation implies a change in value creation, stemming from the digital technologies adopted to transform this business model. Companies need to reconsider their business scope and identify potential new revenue streams from digitally enhanced products, services, and customer interactions (Hess et al. 2016; Matt et al. 2014). Technology decisions are critical in the introduction of new emerging technologies into the company. The role that technology plays in companies is to achieve strategic goals. Roles that allow for new business opportunities are only supportive of meeting current business needs. The company's attitude towards new technologies and their ability to exploit them for future business purposes. Companies typically fall into two broad categories: they adopt established and widely used technology solutions and act as market followers or become market leaders by innovating and introducing new technology solutions to the market. Strategic decisions must be taken in the change of interactions with customers. Companies are encouraged to investigate the potential new benefits created by having a customer experience with enhanced digital changes on customer history. This can be achieved by tracking all customer touchpoints and physically integrating enterprise interactions across multiple digital platforms. Managerial decisions have a financial element that evolves around how to finance digital transformation efforts, after assessing the financial pressures on businesses today. Focusing on innovation development is an important element, as managers are encouraged to see digital innovation as an integral part of their strategy. Organizational decisions identify companies to be

able to see employees, culture, talents, skills, and leadership more closely. Companies need to review the need to develop collaborative work environments and ensure that transformation projects are managed properly. Structural decisions involve proper internal governance as well as external collaboration through partnerships or acquisitions. Internally, companies face many structural choices to support the implementation of their digital transformation strategy and to make decisions about which new operations to incorporate into their existing structures or through new, separate units. Externally the company collects the necessary knowledge during takeovers in the form of mergers and acquisitions activities. Companies can also develop their workforce in digital technology through fostered partnerships. Operational decisions cannot be ignored in digital transformation projects and primarily incorporate choices regarding the operational changes required to adapt to today's business processes.

Strategy Process; (1) Types, the type of strategy process determines the focus of the strategy used or describes the managerial perspective. Two types of strategies identified in the work start the digital transformation journey by; Customer Engagement Strategy (CES) and Digitization Solutions Strategy (DSS). The customer engagement strategy focuses on offering a superior, innovative, personalized, and integrated customer experience. Meanwhile, the digitalization solution strategy aims to reformulate the company's value proposition through the integration of products, services, and data. (2) Paths; Some suggested paths can guide companies in choosing a starting point for their digital transformation journey. There are three strategic paths as a starting point in digital transformation. The starting point for the path evolves around reshaping the operating model by leveraging information and digital capabilities within the organization before reshaping the value proposition and customer experience through digitally enhanced products and services. The second path begins by changing the value proposition before reshaping the operating model and alternative routes. The third begins by changing both of them simultaneously from the start. (3) Configurations; A strategic configuration is followed when companies adopt new technologies to help them transform. The process of identifying different techniques to use with a direct impact on the external environment, the internal environment, or both. (4) Participants; Key participants in digital transformation that need to be known during the strategy formulation and implementation process. The broad nature of digital transformation and its alignment with multiple levels of strategy sees cross-functional integration within the business. The actors must collaborate in adapting to technology. (5) Frameworks Digital transformation strategy frameworks require much of the strategic content discussed earlier and are all designed in stages and built on each other. This supports the idea that transformation is the process that brings the company forward.

Business Model

Business model is one of the management concepts where this concept describes how companies are created and get value (Radostina, 2015). Business model is defined as the core logic by which companies create customer value (Fleisher, 2007). Business model is said to be a method or a way, business model is also interpreted as a component. The components in question are several parts of the business that are grouped into several parts so that it makes it easier to analyze a business. Some of these parts are who is served, what will be

offered, how to produce products, how to make money or profit, and the last is how to distinguish itself strategically from competitors (Nasution, 2016).

Before building its business, a company should be able to create a business design that can help the company in decisions making. One of the tools in designing a business design is the business model canvas (BMC). BMC is an overview of what the company must do to facilitate the stages of the company in managing its business. BMC can assist businesses in knowing the elements of the business model, the interrelationships between the elements, and the impact of its value creation (Joyce, 2016).

- Customer Segment

Customer segment, a person or a party that plays the most important role in its contribution to providing income for the company this party can be consumers or customers where consumers buy products or services offered by the company (Nasution, 2016). It can be said that the customer segment is the party targeted by the company to be served on the company's offering and can provide benefits for the company.

- Value Proposition.

Value proposition refers to the value offered by the company in the specified market segment (Nasution, 2016). This stage is more about what makes customers choose the company's products, what uniqueness makes the customers choose the products in facilitating their daily activities.

- Channels

Channel, is an element that has a direct relationship with the company's intermediary facilities with the consumer segment that has been targeted by the company before (Nasution, 2016). The function of the channel is to mediate communication between the company and consumers who have been targeted or it can be said that channel is how the company reaches customers (Priyono, 2015).

- Customer Relationships

Customer relationships are the company's strategy to establish and strengthen bonds with targeted consumers (Nasution, 2016). This type of relationship is a company's way of keeping consumers' loyalty to the company to keep on using the products or services offered.

- Revenue Stream

The revenue stream is a company's main source of income and profits. This element is a way how the company can manage incoming cash flow by managing the resources owned by the company in order to make maximum efforts to get profits (Nasution, 2016). According to (Priyono, 2015) revenue does not only come from the sale of goods and services it can also be obtained from asset rentals. Revenue streams can also be interpreted as revenue obtained from customer segments.

- Key Activities

Key activities are the important activities or core activities carried out by the company to be successful (Priyono, 2015). This core activity is about how the company can produce a product or service offering that can be offered to buyers who have been targeted.

- Key Resources

Key resources are the resources owned by the company. In other words, key resources are the core assets or the most important assets that are needed by the company to make the company successful (Nasution, 2016).

- Key Partnerships

Key partners are interpreted as the resources needed by the company but not owned by the company, then the company needs cooperation with other parties to be able to complete the lack of resources needed by the company (Nasution, 2016).

- Cost Structure

The cost structure is an element that measures all costs incurred, borne to produce, market, and provide value to its consumers (Nasution, 2016).

Research Methodology

This research uses a descriptive method that has the purpose of describing, explaining, and validating how scientific and social phenomena are the object of research. Researchers are expected to achieve goals after successfully describing the characteristics or behaviors of individuals or social groups studied. Descriptive research focuses on describing the nature of demographic segments, without focusing on the "why" do certain phenomena occur. Descriptive research is aimed at highlighting a problem through a data collection process that allows researchers to describe situations more fully and in detail. The study deals with observation, but researchers have no restrictions on data collection. In essence, the study aims to describe the characteristics and/or behavior of the sample population studied. This research uses a qualitative research approach whereby the study intends to understand the phenomenon of what the research subject is experiencing. This approach can be said to be an approach that is carried out focusing on the research subject which then the results of the approach are outlined in the form of written words empirical data obtained.

Research methods are defined as scientific ways to obtain data with specific purposes and uses. Research methods are used to get data according to needs (Sugiyono, 2010). The research method used by the researcher is case study which focuses on a detailed case (Surachman, 1982). Case studies are also interpreted as research on an event or event that arises due to the occurrence of the phenomenon that occurs. Case studies also outline comprehensive explanations of various aspects of individuals, groups, organizations, programs, or social situations. This research was conducted to have the means for digging deeper information in detail on the object of the study, namely hijab fashion store Malya Indonesia. The case study in this study seeks to find the scientific truth of digital business models in hijab fashion Malya Indonesia by studying deeper and over a longer period of time. The accuracy and sharpness of the researchers are needed in the process of data retrieval and management to be the basis for consideration of conclusion withdrawal and recommendation of suggestions for research objects from the researchers.

Data Source

Primary data is data that has never been collected by anyone before. This primary data refers only to information obtained or collected directly by the researcher from the intended research object. This data source

can be obtained from interviews, questionnaires, and observations of events on the ground. In this study, primary data was obtained from the field observation process to Malya Indonesia stores and the interview process to Malya Indonesia business actors.

Secondary data is data collected and compiled by others or researchers before so that it can be used as important information for researchers in conducting their research. Secondary data can be obtained from the results of previous research, data published by the government, websites, and other information derived from the internet. In this study, secondary data was obtained through the study of documents and data from the internet. In addition, supporting data from the company complement the data that has been obtained from previous primary data sources.

Data Collection Technique

Observation is a technique of collecting data done through surveillance, accompanied by recordings of the conditions that occur in the field. The observation process is carried out by systematically monitoring and recording the symptoms or phenomena that occur to be studied. The method of collecting observational data can be intended as a way of retrieving data through direct observation of the situation or events in the field which in this study is directly plunged into the Malya Indonesia's store.

An interview is one of the techniques of collecting data through a one-way oral question and answer process, which means the question comes from the person asking the source. Interviews are a form of direct communication between researchers and respondents. Communication takes place in the form of Q&A in a face-to-face relationship, so the verbal words will be the complementary media pillar. By interviewing, the source person will share information and experiences with the interviewer. Interviews can be structured and unstructured. A structured interview is where the interviewer has a list of questions to ask the source person, while an unstructured one is where the interviewer directly asks the source person without making a list of questions.

Document studies are material written in the form of books, journals that discuss the topic studied. Document studies help researchers to see ideas, opinions, and criticisms about the topic that were previously constructed and analyzed by previous researchers. The importance of document studies is to look at and analyze the added value of this research compared to previous studies.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data reduction is summarizing, choosing some of the main things that are considered important, focusing on important things, looking for themes and patterns, and discarding those that are less needed. The reduced data can provide a clearer picture that will make it easier for researchers to collect data next. Presentation of data is a set of information that is arranged systematically and easily understood in the form of brief descriptions, charts, relationships between categories, flowcharts, and so on. Conclusion withdrawal is the last stage in data analysis. It is done by looking at the results of fixed data reduction which refers to the formulation of the problem in the goal to be achieved. The data that has been compiled is compared between one and the other to be drawn conclusions in response to the identification of existing problems.

Analysis

Malya Indonesia's Digital Transformation Design in context, content and process

All aspects of internal encouragement entirely occur in Malya Indonesia. Behind the Covid-19 pandemic as a disaster, the company was able to actually cut so many expenses. Among other things, currently, Malya Indonesia only pays one employee as a fixed cost and raw materials, tailors, couriers as variable costs. The absence of distance and time limits makes it possible for everyone to buy Malya Indonesia's products anytime and from anywhere. The sales drop was the main reason for Malya Indonesia to perform digital transformation but eventually, the company realized that this aspect was only one of the other encouragements. Internal supports also bring the company to interact more closely with buyers because the company can read buyers' interests. In addition, the company can also communicate directly with buyers via chat or the provided criticism and suggestions column. Meanwhile, Malya Indonesia also fulfills all aspects of the external drive on why the company needs to perform the digital transformation. Malya Indonesia is required to be sensitive to technological developments that demand changes in the business order because maybe one day there will be no more offline stores that need to rent physical stores. Another aspect is that digital transformation indirectly helps the company in serving buyers and staying connected with the buyers. In this case, Malya Indonesia can serve all new and old buyers. The company can also perform after-sales service according to the buyer's interest. The company also needs to compete with competitors who have made their first transformation in order to still survive in the market. Basically, digital transformation helps the company with its sales because it is supported by so many startup companies, such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Fintech (OVO), banking, and delivery services such as Gojek.

Malya Indonesia started the transformation in 2016. This was done by using social media as another means of selling. Besides being used as a catalog intended for buyers to easily see the collection of products, buyers can also order directly via Instagram. However, it is now easier for buyers to purchase the products using Shopee or Tokopedia, so buyers can easily view catalogs, product descriptions, product availability in warehouses, testimonials, and even payment transactions that can be done directly at Shopee or Tokopedia. Buyers can also compare Malya Indonesia's products with its competitors through Shopee or Tokopedia. Unfortunately, the management of the company's Instagram, Shopee, and Tokopedia is not too optimal that the catalog presented is not updated. Besides having no updated catalog, Malya Indonesia is also not very active in participating in special events that have been offered by Shopee or Tokopedia such as 11.11 or other major holiday celebrations. When compared to several competitors or buttonscares market leaders who have their own website, Malya Indonesia is considered quite far behind and has not transformed optimally.

The strategic process aspect of the company uses an approach where the company performs digital transformation by transforming its type of business. Malya Indonesia has carried out two types of strategy processes, namely Customer Engagement Strategy (CES) and Digital Solution Strategy (DSS). By interacting with product offerings that adjust the products offered, the company has carried out the Customer Engagement Strategy (CES) which was generated after the Digital Solution Strategy (DSS) was carried out. Both types of

strategy are necessary to be applied and not interchangeably. It is because both strategies are interrelated, by implementing the Digital Solution Strategy, the Customer Engagement Strategy will also be implemented in the company.

Malya Indonesia's Digital-Based Business Model Design

There are several changes when comparing BMC before and after the company has made a digital transformation. There are several unchanged aspects such as the value proposition, customer relationships, and revenue streams, while other aspects changed. Starting from key activities, the main activity is no longer focused on maintaining product quality and ensuring inventory in the warehouse but also branding on Shopee, Tokopedia, and Instagram. The Key Partner aspect is multiplied by using Shopee and Tokopedia and of course, all sales transactions are carried out using fintech, such as e-wallet Shopeepay, GoPay, Ovo, and transactions using BCA and BNI mobile banking. Changes in key resources aspects are also multiplied, by utilizing the customer database as the company's core resource and having only one employee. The channel aspect is reduced by eliminating the offline store because all sales activities focused on the online store. The customer segment aspect, due to the absence of time and distance limits in sales, Malya Indonesia can sell its products anywhere and anytime. The last one is the cost structure aspect, which changes a lot by reducing from six employees to one employee, making the company more efficient. In addition, shop rental fees, electricity, water, security, transport, parking, garbage, and others are no longer counted. Instead, the company pays e-commerce fees from Shopee and Tokopedia with a certain amount of percentage.

Business Model Canvas-Malya Indonesia				
Key Partners	Key Activities	Value Propositions	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabric Supplier; Median Textile • E-Commerce; Shopee & Tokopedia • E-Wallet; Shopeepay, OVO, Mobile Banking (BCA & BNI) • Tailor; Makloon • Courir; Gojek, Anteraja, JNE, J&T • Designer • Endorse Celebrity; Natasha Rizki, Adelia Pasha, Mama Amy, Shezy Idris. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media & Marketplace (Shopee & Tokopedia) Branding • Quality Control Product • Inventory of Good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Premium Product (Voal Print Scarf) • Unique Design • Affordable Product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discount item • Reward for seller 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female Muslim • Middle Class • Age; 40 above
	Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer Database • Reseller • Admin 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-Commerce; Shopee & Tokopedia • Social Media; Instagram & WhatsApp Business 	
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing cost; Endorsment Celebrity, Shopee & Tokopedia Fee • Fabric Cost; raw materials • Salary; Fix Salary; Admin, Variable Salary; Tailor, Courir, Designer • Miscellaneous; electricity, water, stationery & packing equipment 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sales to buyers and reseller 		

Therefore, the existence of digital transformation facilitates both the company and buyers. It can be seen that a lot of expenses can be reduced and sales become more effective. It's just that the human resources that manage the digitalization carried out by the company have not been maximized. There are a lot of opportunities that can be explored by the company that are not utilized properly.

Conclusions

The aspects of internal support entirely occur in Malaya Indonesia. Behind the Covid-19 pandemic as a disaster, the company can actually cut so many expenses. The sales drop was the main reason for Malya Indonesia to carry out digital transformation but eventually, the company realized that this aspect was only one of the other encouragements. Digital transformation indirectly helps the company in serving buyers staying connected with the buyers. Malya Indonesia started the transformation in 2016. This was done by using social media as another means of selling. Besides being used as a catalog intended for buyers to easily see the collection of products, buyers can also order directly via Instagram. The company carries out digital transformation by transforming its type of business. Malya Indonesia has carried out two types of strategy processes, namely Customer Engagement Strategy (CES) and Digital Solution Strategy (DSS). With the company's unchanged product offering, Malya Indonesia no longer has to pay for shop rental, electricity, water, security, transport, parking, garbage, and others. Instead, they pay e-commerce fees from Shopee and Tokopedia with a certain amount of percentage.

Suggestions

Maximizing the management of Instagram, Shopee, and Tokopedia. Besides branding, the company also needs to manage its online store. The company needs to have human resources who understand and are

aware of the changing times and digitalization. Catalog management, product updates, marketing, digital transactions need to be maximized properly. As for making an official website, the company can input various kinds of information that are usually needed by customers regarding the products the company offers. Besides, a website can also be a central online store with all data and offers from the company. For this reason, the company's website must be accessible from anywhere and anytime so that both the company and the buyers can easily access it.

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